

EMPIRICAL USE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS FOCUSING ON WAVES (EUPHORBIA TIRUCALLI) IN THE QUILOMBOLA COMMUNITY OF NUGUAÇU IN THE STATE OF BAHIA

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ABSTRACT

The district of Nuguaçu is located 22 km from the municipality of Mirangaba (state of Bahia), it was recognized as a remnant Quilombo community (or Quilombola community) in 2011. The population is mostly made up of elderly people and by children. The Quilombola community of Nuguaçu, like other Quilombola communities, practices customs of their ancestors, among these customs the use of medicinal plants as an alternative for the cure and treatment of pathologies. The objective of this work was to understand the level of knowledge of the population of Nuguaçu about the use of medicinal plants and in particular the avélos plant known scientifically as *Euphorbia tirucalli*.

Keywords: Aveloz, avelós, remnants of Quilombos, medicinal plants, african plant.

RESUMO

The district of Nuguauçu is located 22 km from the municipality of Mirangaba (state of Bahia), it was recognized as a remnant Quilombo community (or Quilombola community) in 2011. The population is mostly made up of elderly people and children. The Quilombola community of Nuguauçu, like other Quilombola communities, practices customs of their ancestors, among these customs the use of medicinal plants as an alternative for the cure and treatment of pathologies. Therefore, the objective of this work was to understand the level of knowledge of the population of Nuguauçu about the use of medicinal plants and in particular the Avélos plant known scientifically as *Euphorbia tirucalli*.

Palavras-chave: Aveloz, Avelós, remanescente de Quilombos, plantas medicinais, planta africana.

INTRODUCTION

Africans, along with Indians, were responsible for forming the base of empirical and cultural knowledge about medicinal plants in Brazil. Enslaved Africans played two roles in this historical process: transplanting an African botanical classification system and introducing native Brazilian plants into their own culture through their symbolic medicinal effects (ALMEIDA, 2011). Dissatisfaction and indignation with the conditions to which black Africans were subjected in Brazil led to the creation of geographic sites where these peoples grouped against the slave system of the time. These communities were called quilombos. Such Quilombos (or Quilombolas) communities last until the present day, with ethnic-racial groups of black ancestry and their own historical and cultural characteristics, as well as their ancestors, the use of medicinal plants is very common in these communities.

The district of Nuguauçu is located 22 km from the municipality of Mirangaba (state of Bahia), it was recognized as a remnant Quilombo community (or Quilombola community) in 2011, by the president of the Quilombo Association Oliveira Francisco. The community is better known in the surroundings as Campo do Meio, it is a small community, with few houses (PREFEITURA DE MIRANGABA,

2023). The population consists mostly of elderly people and children. Young people in general emigrate to other regions to study or work and return only during the vacation period. Most of the Quilombola population of Nuguaçu survives on family farming, mainly beans, cassava and corn. Due to the fact that the majority of the population residing in the community is elderly, income from pensions is significant for the local economy (PREFEITURA DE MIRANGABA, 2023).

The community has only one paved street, although the community has access to electricity and piped water, most houses are adobe, and few have sanitary facilities. In the health area, it has a Family Health Program Unit (PREFEITURA DE MIRANGABA, 2023). The Quilombola community of Nuguaçu, like other Quilombola communities, practices customs of their ancestors, among these customs the use of medicinal plants as an alternative for the cure and treatment of pathologies.

In this sense, this article aims to understand the level of knowledge of the population of Nuguaçu about the use of medicinal plants and the therapeutic and toxic properties of these plants, and in particular the Avélos plant known scientifically as *Euphorbia tirucalli*, which is a plant originating in from Africa and very common in northeastern Brazil.

METHODOLOGY

This study is a quantitative and qualitative research with the application of structured interviews. Quantitative studies are based on the collection and analysis of numerical data and subsequent interpretation of results. In turn, qualitative studies seek to understand and describe social phenomena from the analysis of non-numerical data, such as open interviews, participant observation, among others. Structured interviews are a data collection technique in which the researcher previously prepares a script of questions to be applied to the participants.

For the development of the research, there were following some phases:

Bibliographic survey in relation to the community:

In order, to learn more about the community, research was carried out related to its population, economy and culture. With a visit to the Municipality of Mirangaba-Bahia, territory that is home to the Quilombola community of Nuguaçu. There was also research of local documents about the community.

Visit the Nuguaçu community *in loco*:

To understand more about the local culture as well as the way of life of the population, economic and physical structure. A previous visit was made to the community of Nuguaçu.

Development and application of the questionnaire:

A structured questionnaire was developed with six objective questions and two questions of a qualitative nature, the questionnaire evaluated the degree of knowledge of the people in relation to medicinal plants: botanical data, therapeutic properties, toxic properties and form of use, with emphasis on Alvelos.

On the second visit to the community of Nuguaçu, for the application of the questionnaire, structured interviews were carried out with residents, who were chosen at random. The inclusion criterion to participate in the research was to be a resident of the Community since birth and have ancestors also residing in the community. Be over 18 years old and have agreement and acceptance with the research.

Statistical analysis:

Statistical analysis was descriptive, with quantitative variables and using position measurements. Then, from the analyzed data, graphs and tables were developed, better presentation of the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Regarding the sociodemographic data of the popular people of the Quilombola Community of Nuguaçu, 17% of the interviewees were between 18 and 30 years old, 11% were between 31 and 45 years old, 39% were between 46 and 60 years old and 33% were over 60 years old (Figure 1), that is, 72% of the interviewees were over 46 years old, corroborating with data obtained through the Mirangaba city (2023), that the elderly population is the majority in the community, and that some young people who still reside, usually work, and have leisure in the surrounding municipalities (PREFEITURA DE MIRANGABA, 2023).

Figure 1: Age of the people interviewed in the Quilombola Community of Nuguaçu.

The popular use of medicinal plants is an ancient practice, which has been propagated by successive generations. And in Quilombola communities, the cultivation of medicinal plants is an alternative to primary health care. In Nuguaçu, when asked about the use of medicinal plants in a therapeutic way, 89% of respondents reported making common use of medicinal plants, while only 11% prefer industrialized medicines, justifying having chronic pathologies and mobility difficulties to collect plants.

Medicinal plants are capable of alleviating or curing illnesses (BRASIL, 2000). Plants are a rich source of secondary metabolites that can serve in the treatment or prevention of diseases. These are widely used in integrative medicine, as they are more accessible and inexpensive, especially in tropical and developing countries (GADELHA, 2013).

When asked about how long they have been using medicinal plants and which are the main plants they use on a daily basis, most report that they have been using medicinal plants since childhood, having learned this practice from their parents and grandparents. Of the main medicinal plants reported by the people, there are: Lemon balm, Rosemary, Umburanas and Jatobá bark, plants widely cultivated in the community.

Of the interviewees, 100% answered that they make frequent use of Lemon Balm (*Melissa officinalis* L), a plant belonging to the *Lamiaceae* family, which originates in Asia and Europe, was brought to Brazil over a hundred years ago and is now cultivated in All country. *M. officinalis* is considered a plant for medicinal use because of the active principles of its composition, the essential oil, tannins, flavonoids, glycosides and rosmarinic acids and the beta and alpha citral compounds, all essential to trigger the pharmacological effect of the plant (MASIERO et al., 2021). The leaves of this plant are used as an infusion in the treatment of various diseases. Its main functions are antiplatelet, bactericidal, antifungal, antiviral, herbicide, pesticide, antiseptic, insecticide and flavoring effects. All this due to its main chemical constituent eugenol and cariofilenol (ACEVEDO et al., 2013).

Avelós (*Euphorbia tirucalli*), a plant originally from the African continent, is used as ornamental and medicinally. In the Quilombola community Nuguauçu, the cultivation of Avelós is intense, mainly being used as a living fence, this plant was culturally introduced in quilombola communities by their African ancestors (ALMEIDA, 2011). When the residents of Nuguauçu were asked if they knew the Avelós plant (*Euphorbia tirucalli*), in order to avoid confusion regarding the accuracy of the plant, photos were shown to the interviewees. 89% of respondents reported knowing the Avelós plant, while only 11% reported not

knowing. *Euphorbia tirucalli*, belonging to the *Euphorbiaceae* family, is present especially in the northeast region (of Brazil) due to its incredible ease of propagation in warm environments, adapting to tropical and subtropical areas of the planet (DE OLIVEIRA; NEPOMUCENO, 2006).

Afterwards, the popular people were asked if they had already used Avélos therapeutically for the treatment of any pathology. 89% said they had never used it medicinally and some even justified never having used it because the plant exhibited toxicity, while 11% reported having already used the plant for medicinal purposes, and that care in preparing it would be important, as they knew the fact that the plant presents toxicity. Avelós latex is known to have the most diverse properties: antiscorpion and snakebite, purgative, anti-inflammatory expectorant, antispasmodic, antimicrobial and antineoplastic action (LAINETTI; BRITTO, 1979). However, the preparation for use must be carried out carefully and diluted in water, and the Hazelnut Latex must never be contacted directly on the skin and/or mucous membranes.

The use of this plant is attributed to 400 BC, but according to Costa (2011), it was only in 1880 to 1890 that the physician Panfilio inserted the plant in “conventional” medicine. Comprehensive studies on *Euphorbia tirucalli* were developed only in the second half of the 21st century, more precisely in the 1980s. When asking: Are there any contraindications in the use of hazelnuts? 39% reported not knowing and/or never having heard of it, 61% reported that Avelos “milk” (latex) can cause blindness, “itch” in the eyes, can “burn”, is toxic to the skin and some associated toxicity (Table 1).

Table 1. Contraindications for the use of hazelnuts according to popular reports.

Are there any contraindications to the use of hazelnuts?
If you scratch your eye, you are blind, you even know people who have had an accident with the plant.
Causes eye irritation

Milk burns and can blind you.

You know milk is toxic.

Have you ever heard that milk makes you blind?

According to Fiocruz's National Toxicological Information System, latex, when in contact with the skin and mucous membranes, can cause lesions, edema in the lips, mouth, burning pain and itching. When ingested, it can cause nausea, vomiting and diarrhea, with reports of death occurring. Direct contact with the eyes can cause irritation, tearing, eyelid edema and vision difficulties (MARTINATO, 2021). Sauaia Filho (2018) reports that in 1968, the northeastern physician Lauro Neiva recommended to his patients the dilution of 6 drops of Avelós latex in 2 liters of water and that they drink it for a period of 3 days, aiming at the treatment of pathologies such as the cancer. Through studies carried out on the plant, low levels of predation were observed and an enormous resistance to pests and pesticides as a result of the toxic potential of its latex, leading to the conclusion that the medicinal properties of *Euphorbia tirucalli* are present in the stem and leaves of the plant.

It is estimated that across the country there are more than three thousand quilombola communities, present in at least 24 states, according to Dalt & Brandão (2011). It is noticed that the population of the Quilombola Nuguauçu community, like most traditional Quilombola communities, preserves the culture that their ancestors brought from Africa in terms of religious practices, physical and spiritual health care (ANJOS, 2000). In the field of health, he makes constant use of medicinal plants in a therapeutic way and has empirical knowledge about the use of these plants. According to the interviews carried out in the research, elderly and young people living in the community use medicinal plants. Citing mainly cultivated and common plants in the region.

Regarding knowledge about the Avelos plant (*Euphorbia tirucalli*), community members report knowing the plant and its therapeutic properties, and some

users report the appearance of toxic reactions involving the use of its latex, which makes the use of the plant for medicinal purposes little incident.

CONCLUSION

In Quilombola communities there is cultural preservation of habits and routines of ancestors, which makes clear the use of medicinal plants in the treatment of diseases, being more used than pharmaceutical drugs. This article allows us to conclude that the Nuguacu community is characterized and similar in habits and customs to other Quilombola communities, making constant use of medicinal plants in situations of the simplest pathologies, also cultivating these plants, mainly those typical of the region. And in relation to the use of Avélos, which according to the literature itself, despite having therapeutic properties, also has toxicity, the quilombolas in general, through empirical and cultural knowledge, demonstrate to know such properties and toxicities.

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